

1 **Genome sequencing and assembly of *Phytophthora oleae*, isolate VK10A, causative agent**
2 **of rot of olive drupes.**

3 **Authors:** Sebastiano Conti Taguali^{1,2}, Mario Riolo¹, Federico La Spada¹, Santa Olga
4 Cacciola^{1*}, Giuseppe Dionisio^{3*}

5 ¹ Catania University, Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment (UniCT, Di3A), Via
6 S. Sofia 100, 95123 Catania (Italy).

7 ² Mediterranea University of Reggio Calabria, Department of Agricultural Science, Località
8 Feo di Vito, 89122 Reggio di Calabria (Italy).

9 ³ Aarhus University, Department of Agroecology, section of Crop Biotechnology and
10 Genetics, Forsoegsvej 1, 4200 Slagelse (Denmark)

11 * Corresponding authors: giuseppe.dionisio@agro.au.dk; olga.cacciola@unict.it

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13 The genus *Phytophthora*, often referred to as "plant destroyers," is a taxon of oomycetes
14 including several species well known for causing devastating plant diseases (Erwin and
15 Ribeiro, 1996). The genus *Phytophthora* is rapidly expanding (Brasier et al. 2022) and, despite
16 the discordance between molecular phylogeny and morphology-based taxonomy, it is well-
17 recognized and organized in multiple phylogenetic clades encompassing more than 223 taxa
18 (Abad et al. 2023).

19 The genus includes many economically important species that affect a wide range of
20 plant hosts, including vegetables, fruit and nut trees, forest trees, and nursery crops.
21 *Phytophthora oleae* is a newly identified species within the *Phytophthora* genus
22 (NCBI:txid2107226), known for causing significant diseases in plants, particularly in olives.
23 This pathogen has been isolated from rhizosphere soil and roots of olive trees with root rots as
24 well as from rotten drupes. *Phytophthora oleae* affects wild and cultivated olive trees in
25 Mediterranean regions, notably in Italy and Spain (Ruano-Rosa et al., 2018; González et al.,
26 2019).

27 In Spain, *P. oleae* has been identified as a pathogen causing severe decline in wild olive
28 (*Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris*) forests, which are of high ecological value and serve as a key
29 genetic source for olive improvement programs (González et al., 2019). The pathogen was
30 consistently isolated from the rootlets of symptomatic wild olives in a protected forest,
31 alongside other *Phytophthora* species, such as *P. cryptogea* and *P. megasperma* (González et
32 al., 2019). The identification of *P. oleae* was confirmed through morphological analysis and
33 genetic sequencing of the ITS regions and *cox1* sequences (González et al., 2019;
34 <https://idtools.org/phytophthora/index.cfm?entityID=5133&packageID=1131>). Notably, *P.*
35 *oleae* exhibits a maximum growth at a relatively low temperature of 19.9°C on carrot agar
36 medium, distinguishing it from other *Phytophthora* species affecting olives (González et al.,
37 2019). The pathogenicity of *P. oleae* was confirmed on healthy wild olive seedlings, indicating
38 its potential threat not only to wild olive populations, but also to cultivated olive orchards,
39 especially considering the climate change scenario and rainfall patterns in southern Spain
40 (González et al., 2019).

41 In southern Italy, *P. oleae* has been associated with rot of mature olive drupes in two
42 local cultivars of olive (Brasier et al., 2022; Ruano-Rosa et al., 2018), indicating its role in
43 determining significant damages to olive production. The identification of *P. oleae* as a

44 pathogen of both fruit and roots underscores its versatility and the potential of this species to
45 jeopardize the olive cultivation in the Mediterranean.

46 In this study, *P. oleae* VK10A has been isolated from a rotten olive drupe collected from
47 a wild olive (*Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris*) tree belonging to the Complesso Speleologico
48 Villasmundo S. Alfio Nature Reserve (NR) (Melilli, Siracusa, Italy; DATUM WGS 84,
49 37°13'17.2"N 15°06'22.3"E). Species identity of the isolate VK10A was confirmed through
50 amplification, sequencing, and BLAST analysis of the Internal Transcriber Spacer regions of
51 the ribosomal DNA. Results showed that the ITS sequence of the isolate VK10A had a 100%
52 identity with of the *P. oleae* isolate Po2a (CBS7670, GenBank accession KY982934.1),
53 paratype of the *P. oleae* type isolate Po1a (ex-type: CBS7669), belonging to clade 2d (Ruano-
54 Rosa et al., 2018; Jung et al., 2024).

55 For genomic sequencing, a four-day-old culture of *P. oleae* isolate VK10A grown in
56 Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) was subjected to gDNA extraction by using DNeasy PowerSoil
57 Pro kit (Qiagen, Denmark) according to the manufacturer's protocol. The obtained gDNA
58 fragments were in the range of 14-22 kbp with no discernible small fragments judging from
59 Bioanalyzer analysis (Agilent Technologies, Denmark). DNA concentrations and purities were
60 measured with the Qubit dsDNA HS Assay kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and the
61 NanoDrop One (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). DNA size distributions were evaluated using
62 the Genomic DNA ScreenTapes on the Agilent TapeStation 4200 (Agilent, USA).

63 Library preparation was carried out using the ligation sequencing kits (Oxford
64 Nanopore Technologies, UK) on a barcoded SQK-LSK114.24 DNA library prepared according
65 to the manufacturer's protocol, with minor modifications (DNAsense ApS, Aalborg, Denmark)
66 (Sereika et al., 2022). The barcoded DNA library (approximately 10-20 fmol) was loaded onto
67 a primed FLO-MIN114 flow cell and sequenced on a MinION Mk1b device, running
68 MinKNOW v. 23.04.5. FAST5 signal data was base-called and demultiplexed with Guppy v.
69 6.5.7 (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, Oxford, United Kingdom) using the super-accurate
70 algorithm (dna_r10.4.1_e8.2_400bps_5khz_sup.cfg). Removal of low-quality reads and
71 generation of basic sequencing data statistics were obtained using Nanoq v. 0.9.0 (Steinig and
72 Coin, 2021).

73 Filtered reads were de novo assembled with Flye (Kolmogorov et al., 2019 and 2020)
74 polished once with Medaka (<https://github.com/nanoporetech/medaka>). Subsequently, the
75 ONT data was polished with Illumina 350 PE, 1-2Gb (approximately 4-7M reads) data using
76 Racon (via Minimap and Samtools). The draft assembly was subsequently polished twice with
77 Medaka v. 1.8.0. Assembly graphs were inspected with Bandage v. 0.8.1 (Wick et al., 2015).
78 Contigs below 1000 bp were removed with SeqKit v. 2.2.0 (Shen et al., 2016). BUSCO v. 5.2.2
79 (Manni et al., 2021) was used to evaluate genome completion. Quality-filtered Illumina and
80 Nanopore reads were classified with Kaiju v. 1.9.2 (Menzel et al., 2016) against the subset of
81 GenBank proteins *nr* eukaryotic database.

82 In summary, to obtain genetic and mRNA information for *P. oleae* VK10A, it was
83 performed both Oxford Nanopore Sequencing (ONT) and Illumina short read sequencing of
84 gDNA to polish the reads and RNAseq de novo assembly. Other *Phytophthora* species genome
85 size span from 228.5 Mbp (e.g. *P. infestans*, reference genome ASM14294v1), to 165.6 Mbp
86 (e. g. *P. palmivora*, PpalZC01v1) or from 101.5 Mbp (e. g. *P. megakarya*, ASM221536v1) to
87 59 Mbp (e. g. *P. nicotianae*, ASM332846v1) or less. The *P. oleae* VK10A raw ONT statistics
88 are displayed in Table 1, and the *de-novo* genome assembly statistics are given in Table 2.

90 **Table 1 – *P. oleae* ONT genomic DNA sequencing statistics.** Sequencing ID denotes the
 91 sequencing nomenclature assigned by DNASense ApS company (Denmark). Extraction conc.
 92 (ng/μL) denotes the measured concentration of double-stranded DNA. Data (Mb) denotes the
 93 data yield and the number of generated reads. Read N50 (bp) is the value where half of the data
 94 is contained within reads of length N50 or greater. Quality score denotes the median Phred-
 95 scaled read quality score.

ID	gDNA conc. (ng/μL)	Raw			Trimmed		
		Data (Mbp)	Read N50 (bp)	Quality score	Data (Mbp)	Read N50 (bp)	Quality score
DJ1425- <i>P. oleae</i> VK10A	12	10358	7364	18.6	6701	7562	20.5

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97 **Table 2 - *P. oleae* ONT genomic DNA assembly statistics.** Contigs denote the number of
 98 contiguous DNA elements associated with the assembly. Assembly size (Mbp) and Largest
 99 contig (Mbp) denote the size of the final assembly and the length of the longest contig,
 100 respectively. Contig n50 (kbp) is the value where half of the assembly is contained within
 101 contigs of length N50 or greater. GC content (%) denotes the mean content of the G and C
 102 nucleotides. DJ1425-barcode12 = *P. oleae* VK10A genome barcode.

Sequencing ID	Contigs	Assembly length (Mbp)	Largest contig (Mbp)	GC content (%)	Contig N50 (kbp)
DJ1424- <i>P. oleae</i> VK10A	168	43.7	2.05	51.82	684

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104 A quantitative assessment of the assembly was carried out using BUSCO
 105 (Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs) scores (Manni et al., 2021). BUSCO
 106 evaluates the completeness of assemblies by looking for the presence or absence of highly
 107 conserved genes (BUSCO orthologs). The *P. oleae* genome assembly was 99% complete
 108 relative to an identified ortholog (*P. plurivora*) that covers the entire length of the alignment
 109 sequence of the corresponding BUSCO benchmarking. *P. oleae* genome assembly was 1%
 110 fragmented which is related to identified orthologs that only partially covers the length of the
 111 sequence alignment. Quality-filtered Illumina and Nanopore reads were already classified with
 112 Kaiju v. 1.9.2, against the GenBank nr protein database (2023-05-10 database, 321 Mio. protein
 113 sequences from both prokaryotes and microbial eukaryotes). The raw fastq files top blast hits
 114 of the *P. oleae* genome was represented by *P. plurivora* (NCBI:txid639000) of which the
 115 genome reference (ASM3002794v1) is composed of 46.9 Mbp. The *P. oleae* genome comprises
 116 43.7 Mbp, and using AUGUSTUS (Stanke and Waack, 2003; Stanke and Morgenstern, 2005)
 117 as gene prediction software, it gave 24836 genes/proteins, some of which represented alternate
 118 spliced isoforms and more than 10% represented alleles, since the isolate VK10A of *P. oleae* is
 119 diploid. Therefore, a consensus based on the most sequenced single nucleotide polymorphism
 120 (SNP) has been collected and the gene annotation GTF file is available for the hisat2/STAR
 121 pipelines for aligning the mRNA to the *P. oleae* reference genome (43.7 Mbp), annotated by
 122 AUGUSTUS web (Stanke and Morgenstern, 2005) using RNAseq *de novo* assembly made by
 123 Trinity assembler (Haas et al., 2013). The AUGUSTUS related proteome was annotated by

124 Mercator4 v5.0 (Lohse et al., 2014) and EffectorP ver3.0 (Sperschneider and Dodds, 2022) and
125 its annotated file is deposited along the first draft of contigs assembly of the *P. oleae* VK10A
126 genome (gDNA and CDS fasta files, gtf, gtf3, and other files) on Zenodo
127 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11092245>). We have annotated 605 apoplastic effectors, and
128 144 with dual localization signals both apoplastic and cytoplasmatic. Besides, we have also
129 found 262 peptidases and 203 proteases into *P. oleae* genome, and 26 avirulence (Avh) protein.
130 From the pathogenicity point of view, we discovered 381 RxLR effectors, 66 Elicitins, 252
131 Crinkler proteins and 16 necrosis inducing proteins (NPP) (Zenodo supplementary excel file,
132 listed in several tabs; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11092245>).

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134 **Data availability:** The *P. oleae* genome assembly has been deposited on Zenodo open access
135 repository as data files under this link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11092245>.

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137 **Conflict of interest:** Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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